

DIGITAL LEARNING BREAKTHROUGH: ELECTRONIC STRATEGIC INTERVENTION MATERIALS (E-SIMS) FOR AN IMPROVED ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE IN ENGLISH 9

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ABSTRACT

The study aimed to investigate the effect of electronic-strategic intervention materials in English 9 and find out whether such intervention materials can improve the mastery level of the students. After the first grading periodic examination, the researchers identified the students who were about to fail the subject. Alongside this, they identified the least mastered learning competencies. To respond to this problem, and to join the MATATAG agenda of the Department of Education, particularly in making the curriculum relevant, the researchers studied the use of E-SIMS. They developed two E-SIMS for the two learning competencies of the first grading period and followed the experimental method to investigate the effectiveness of the E-SIMS in improving the academic performance of the students. Employing a quantitative experimental method, the study found that the students got significantly higher scores in the post-test after the utilization of E-SIMS. The result of the Wilcoxon test shows that the use of E-SIMS as an intervention material has a positive significant effect on the mastery level of the students. Therefore, it is recommended that well-drafted electronic-strategic intervention materials must be utilized as intervention material for English 9. E-SIMS must be used particularly on the competencies that are harder for the students to master.

Keywords: *E-SIM, English Mastery Level, English 9, Effectiveness, GNHS*

INTRODUCTION

The K-12 Curriculum aims to increase students' English competence for communication, academics, and careers. This goal supports the overall goal of improving learners' language skills to prepare them for varied situations and enable global competition. Moreover, the curriculum emphasizes using technology and electronic tools to improve language acquisition, adopting a modern approach to teaching English. Various educators tested the effectiveness of electronic-strategic intervention materials (e-SIM) in their field. For instance, Lazo and de Guzman (2021) found the use of e-SIMs to be effective in Economics. They further concluded that e-SIMs should enhance motivation and facilitate deeper comprehension in the acquisition of learning. De Jesus (2019) investigated the effectiveness of e-SIMs in teaching circulatory and respiratory systems. His study concluded that the e-SIMs significantly improved the academic performance of the students as evidenced by the results of the pre-test and post-test of the students. The current study investigated the effectiveness of e-SIMs in English for students who were failing in terms of improving the mastery level of their least mastered competencies.

Each grading period, the students have a quarterly assessment to assess their proficiency in the learning competencies that were taught and acquired during that specific grading period. Each quarter consists of approximately 5 or 6 learning competencies. During the initial grading period test in English, the researchers determined that modals and conditionals were the two competencies that were least proficiently acquired. The researchers, who were also the teachers in English 9, identified the students who were failing the subject. To assist the students in improving their proficiency in the least mastered skills, the researchers created E-SIMs specifically designed for modals and conditionals. The E-SIMS were distributed to the participating students to assess the efficacy of E-SIMs in enhancing students' academic achievement.

The Department of Education through its Memorandum No.117 s.2005 introduced the use of strategic intervention materials (SIM). Later on, this SIM evolved and became electronic for more effective, efficient, and affordable distribution as it does not necessitate frequent printing or physical distribution. The researchers developed and implemented e-SIMs on modals and conditionals as a proactive measure to improve the mastery level of the students. The materials integrate different multimedia components, interactive quizzes, and captivating exercises. The e-SIM for modals follows the story of Encantadia which is a popular television series based on local folklore whereas the e-SIM for conditionals brings the students to a theme park experience. The students were able to access the e-SIMs through different devices such as cell phones, computers, and tables. For those who had no device, they were allowed to use the big screen in the principal's office. The e-SIMs were designed in such a way that students will require only minimal assistance from the teachers.

Research Questions

This research explored the effect of E-SIMs for Grade 9 English students of Guinayang National High School for the school year 2023-2024. Specifically, this research answered the following questions:

1. What is the mastery level of the student-respondents in English 9 on their pre-test and post-test in terms of:
 - 1.1. Use conditionals in expressing arguments; and
 - 1.2. Express permission, prohibition, and obligation using Modals?
 2. Is there a significant difference between the pre-test and post-test scores of the student respondents?
 3. What is the evaluation of the students and the teachers of the E-SIMs?
 4. Is there a significant difference between the evaluation of the two sets of evaluators?
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METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study utilized the experimental research method which is defined by Bell (2009) as a design that refers to the systematic approach of doing research in a manner that is unbiased and regulated, to maximize accuracy and enable the derivation of precise findings related to a hypothesis statement. The design made appropriate and precise interpretations of the gathered data with the use of statistical methods.

Research Respondents

The researchers selected a group of Grade 9 English students from Guinayang National High School for the academic year 2023-2024. Specifically, these were the students who did not perform well on the English Periodic Test and were at risk of receiving a failing grade in English. From the same test, modals and conditionals were identified as the least mastered competencies. The researchers employed the created E-SIMs on Modals and Conditionals for all 33 students. The data utilized in this study consists of the pre-test and post-test results as well as the evaluation of the e-SIMs by English teachers and students.

Data Collection

The Grade 9 student participants engaged in an experimental study aimed at assessing the effectiveness of E-SIMs as an intervention tool for the English subject. The researchers utilized two e-SIMs to address the two least proficient skills that came out after the first quarterly periodic examination. The e-SIMs were made using Microsoft PowerPoint and all its features. Before engaging in the e-sim, the students were administered a pretest to assess their understanding of the learning skills. Following the intervention, a posttest was conducted to evaluate the impact of the intervention on the

students' learning outcomes. The data was analyzed to determine if there was a significant statistical difference between the participants' pre-test and post-test scores.

The researchers developed the instrument for the pretest and posttest, ensuring its validity and reliability through careful examination. The content underwent validation by English teachers to assess its grammar and construction, and subsequently received validation by official English examination writers. The test had a pilot testing phase with a group of students who were not involved in the study to assess its level of readability and comprehensibility.

Figure 1: Title Card of the e-SIM for Modals

Figure 2: Title Card of the e-SIM for Conditionals

The pretest was administered by the researchers on November 15th. The papers were examined, and the data analysis of the pretest was conducted. Simultaneously, the researchers started the distribution of e-SIMs to the student participants. After the completion of the two e-SIMs, the posttest was administered by the researchers.

Data Analysis

After importing all information from the pretest and posttest of the respondents, the researcher used the following statistical treatment of data:

- To present the scores of the students in their pretest and posttest, the mean and standard deviation were used.
- To test for significant differences between the pre-test and the post-test, the Wilcoxon test was used since the scores were not normally distributed. The Wilcoxon test is a commonly used non-parametric statistical test to compare the means of the same group.

RESULTS and DISCUSSION

1. The mastery level of the student-respondents in English 9 on their pre-test and post-test in terms of:
 - a. (Competency 1) Use conditionals in expressing arguments.
 - b. (Competency 2) Express permission, prohibition, and obligation using Modals

Table 1: Mastery Level of the Respondents in their Pretest

	N	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
Competency 1	33	3.84	2.48	Non-Mastery
Competency 2	33	4.63	2.71	Non-Mastery

Legend: 1.00-7.49 Non-Mastery, 7.50-11.24 Nearing Mastery, 11.25-15.00 Mastery

Table 2: Mastery Level of the Respondents in their Posttest

	N	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
Competency 1	33	13.12	1.38	Mastery
Competency 2	33	13.36	2.08	Mastery

Legend: 1.00-7.49 Non-Mastery, 7.50-11.24 Nearing Mastery, 11.25-15.00 Mastery

Tables 1 and 2 show the mastery level of the respondents on the two competencies before and after the utilization of the e-SIMs. The students' scores show non-mastery for both competencies before the usage of e-SIMs. This was the problem this research was investigating. Both competencies were taught to the students in the course of the quarter

but the students failed to show mastery of them. Their scores in the posttest, after the e-SIMS were utilized, showed an increase from the pretest. Moreover, the students' scores in the post-test improved from non-mastery to mastery in both competencies.

These findings underscore the effectiveness of targeted interventions in addressing the two competencies. The success seen in improving students' proficiency suggests that the e-SIMS employed were well-suited to the learning objectives, indicating the potential for similar strategies to be implemented in future English classes.

2. The Significant Difference between the Pre-test and Post-test Scores

Table 3: Wilcoxon: Significant Difference between Pretest and Posttest

	N	Mean	SD	Mean Difference	Z Value	P Value	Decision	Remarks
Pretest	33	9.36	4.84	18.33	-5.018	.000 (5.2093E-7)	Reject Ho	Significant
Posttest	33	27.69	2.98					

Legend: If the p-value is less than or equal to 0.05 level of significance, reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho.

Table 3 indicates the test of significant difference between the pretest and post-test of the students. The mean difference between pretest and posttest scores was 18.33, indicating a considerable improvement in students' performance following the e-SIMS utilization. The Z value of -5.018 and the corresponding p-value of less than 0.05 indicate that the difference between pretest and posttest scores is statistically significant. Thus, the improvement observed in the post-test scores is a result of using the e-SIMS. This indicates that the e-SIMS were effective as interventions in improving the knowledge and skills of the students in both competencies.

These findings affirm the effectiveness of the e-SIMS in enhancing students' proficiency in the English subject. The significant increase in post-test scores suggests that the e-SIMS employed effectively facilitated learning and skill development among the student respondents.

3. The evaluation of the students and the teachers of the E-SIMS

Table 4: Students' Evaluation of the E-SIMS

e-SIMS Aspects	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Relevance of Content: The content covered in the e-SIMS was relevant and aligned with the learning objectives for modals and conditionals in English 9.	4.80	Strongly Agree
Overall Satisfaction with E-SIMS: I am satisfied with the overall effectiveness of the eSIM for learning modals and conditionals in English 9.	4.50	Agree

Customized Learning: The eSIM provided content and exercises tailored to my specific needs in learning modals and conditionals.	4.40	Agree
Enhancement of Proficiency: The eSIM effectively enhanced my proficiency in using modals and conditionals in English.	4.30	Agree
Clarity of Instruction: The instructions provided in the eSIM were clear and easy to understand.	4.30	Agree
Accessibility and Flexibility: The eSIM was easily accessible from various devices, allowing me to learn at my own pace and convenience.	4.20	Agree
Cost-Effectiveness: The eSIM presented a cost-effective solution for learning modals and conditionals compared to traditional materials.	4.10	Agree
Engagement and Interactivity: The eSIM engaged me through interactive exercises and activities related to modals and conditionals.	4.10	Agree
Interactive Learning: The eSIM incorporated multimedia elements, interactive quizzes, and engaging activities to facilitate learning modals and conditionals.	4.00	Agree
Targeted Remediation: The eSIM specifically addressed areas of difficulty in modals and conditionals, providing focused support for improvement.	4.00	Agree
Empowerment of Self-Directed Learning: The eSIM empowered me to independently improve my understanding and use of modals and conditionals.	4.00	Agree
Retention of Material: The eSIM facilitated better retention of learned material regarding modals and conditionals through various learning techniques.	3.90	Agree
User-Friendly Interface: The eSIM had a user-friendly interface that facilitated easy navigation and use.	3.90	Agree
Flexibility and Accessibility: The eSIM provided flexibility in learning modals and conditionals, accessible from different devices and locations.	3.70	Agree
Progress Tracking: The eSIM provided tools to track my individual progress in learning modals and conditionals.	3.60	Agree
General Mean	4.12	Agree

Legend: 1.00-1.50 Strongly Disagree; 1.51-2.50 Disagree; 2.51-3.50 Neutral; 3.51-4.50 Agree; and 4.51-5.00 Strongly Agree

The feedback from the student respondents regarding various aspects of the e-SIMs for learning modals and conditionals in English 9 shows overall satisfaction. The mean ratings for most aspects range from 3.60 to 4.80, falling within the "Agree" to "Strongly Agree" categories. Notably, respondents strongly agreed on the relevance of the content covered in the e-SIMS, indicating that the e-SIMS met the learning objectives for modals and conditionals. Overall, the e-SIMS received a 4.12 mean with a verbal interpretation of 'agree', suggesting that the students perceive the material to be positively useful in their studies.

Practically, these ratings highlight the perceived positive aspects of the e-SIMS used as an intervention in English classes. The customization aspect, where the e-SIMS provided tailored content and exercises, shows that it caters to individual learning needs, enhancing engagement and effectiveness. Furthermore, its accessibility and flexibility allow learners to access materials from various devices and locations, promote self-directed learning, and accommodate the various paces of learning of the students. Overall, these findings show that the designed e-SIMS were valuable tools for intervention in English 9.

Table 5: English Teachers' Evaluation of the E-SIMS

e-SIMS Aspects	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Customized Learning: The eSIM provided content and exercises tailored to the students' specific needs in learning modals and conditionals.	4.90	Strongly Agree
Interactive Learning: The eSIM incorporated multimedia elements, and interactive and engaging activities to facilitate learning modals and conditionals.	4.90	Strongly Agree
Cost-Effectiveness: The eSIM presented a cost-effective solution for learning modals and conditionals compared to traditional materials as there is no need to print materials anymore.	4.90	Strongly Agree
Enhancement of Proficiency: The eSIM can effectively enhance the students' proficiency in using modals and conditionals in English.	4.90	Strongly Agree
Engagement and Interactivity: The eSIM is engaging enough for the students to go through interactive exercises and activities related to modals and conditionals.	4.90	Strongly Agree
User-Friendly Interface: The eSIM had a user-friendly interface that facilitated easy navigation and use.	4.90	Strongly Agree
Relevance of Content: The content covered in the eSIM was relevant and aligned with the learning objectives for modals and conditionals in English 9.	4.90	Strongly Agree
Overall Satisfaction with E-SIMS: I am satisfied with the overall effectiveness of the eSIM for learning modals and conditionals in English 9.	4.88	Strongly Agree
Accessibility and Flexibility: The eSIM was easily accessible from various devices, allowing the students to learn at their own pace and convenience.	4.80	Strongly Agree
Targeted Remediation: The eSIM specifically addressed areas of difficulty in modals and conditionals, providing focused support for improvement.	4.80	Strongly Agree
Empowerment of Self-Directed Learning: The eSIM can empower the students to independently improve my understanding and use of modals and conditionals.	4.80	Strongly Agree
Clarity of Instruction: The instructions provided in the eSIM were clear and easy to understand.	4.80	Strongly Agree
Progress Tracking: The eSIM provided tools to track the students' individual progress in learning modals and conditionals.	4.60	Strongly Agree
Retention of Material: The eSIM facilitated better retention of learned material regarding modals and conditionals through various learning techniques.	4.60	Strongly Agree

Flexibility and Accessibility: The eSIM provided flexibility in learning modals and conditionals, accessible from different devices and locations. 4.60 Strongly Agree

General Mean **4.81** Strongly Agree

Legend: 1.00-1.50 Strongly Disagree; 1.51-2.50 Disagree; 2.51-3.50 Neutral; 3.51-4.50 Agree; and 4.51-5.00 Strongly Agree

Table 5 shows that the feedback of English teachers regarding various aspects of the e-SIMS is overwhelmingly positive, with mean ratings consistently falling within the "Strongly Agree" category. Notably, respondents strongly agreed that the e-SIMS provided customized learning experiences tailored to their specific needs, indicating a high level of personalization and relevance. The incorporation of multimedia elements and interactive activities was also highly praised, suggesting that the e-SIMS can effectively engage students and promote active learning. Additionally, respondents emphasized the cost-effectiveness of the e-SIMS compared to traditional materials, highlighting the practical benefits of digital resources, such as eliminating the need for printing materials.

The high level of satisfaction regarding the overall effectiveness of the e-SIMS suggests that the designed e-SIMs can positively contribute to the learning outcomes and experiences of the students. Furthermore, the emphasis on accessibility, user-friendliness, and flexibility indicates that the e-SIMS can address different learning styles and preferences, empowering students to engage in self-directed learning and progress at their own pace. Thus, these findings must advocate the integration of e-SIMS into English classes, recognizing their value in providing engaging, personalized, and cost-effective learning experiences that promote proficiency and student success.

4. The Significant Difference between the Evaluation of the Students and the Teachers

Table 6: Wilcoxon: Significant Difference between Students' and Teachers' Evaluation

	N	Mean	SD	Mean Difference	Z Value	P Value	Decision	Remarks
Students	10	4.12	.31	00.69	-2.59	.009	Reject Ho	Significant
Teachers	10	4.81	.33					

Legend: If the p-value is less than or equal to 0.05 level of significance, reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho.

Table 6 shows a significant difference between the evaluation scores provided by students and teachers. Students rated the e-SIMS at 4.12, while teachers provided a higher average rating of 4.81. The mean difference between the evaluations is 0.69. The Z value of -2.59 and the corresponding p-value of 0.009 indicate that this difference is statistically significant at the 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, there is a statistically significant difference in the evaluations of the designed e-SIMS for Grade 9.

While both students and teachers generally give positive evaluations of the e-SIMS, there is a discrepancy in their perceptions. Teachers, on average, rated the e-SIMS more favorably than students. However, understanding and addressing these differences can inform strategies for improving the alignment between teachers' perceptions and students' experiences, ultimately enhancing the effectiveness of interventions.

Conclusions

The results show that the mean of the students' pretest scores is verbally interpreted as 'non-mastery'. Their scores improved in the post-test as their mean is verbally interpreted as 'mastery'. The difference between the pre-test scores and the post-test scores was significant showing that the e-SIMs were effective in improving the mastery level or the test scores of the students.

Moreover, the students' evaluation of the e-SIMs was verbally interpreted as 'agree' while the teachers' evaluation was higher which is verbally interpreted as 'strongly agree'. The difference between the students' and the teachers' evaluations was significant.

Recommendations

In light of the findings, the following recommendations are hereby offered:

1. Utilize e-SIMs both as an Intervention and as a part of English Classes: Given the significant improvement in mastery levels observed after the utilization of e-SIMs, it is recommended to continue employing it to address least mastered competencies in English.
 2. Seminar/Workshop in e-SIMs: To ensure the effective integration of e-SIMs into the teaching and learning process, it is important to invest in seminars and workshops for teachers to learn how to create effective and efficient e-SIMs.
 3. Address the gap between the students' and the teachers' evaluation: The notable difference between student and teacher evaluations emphasizes the need to involve the students in the creation of effective e-SIMs. Establishing channels for feedback and dialogue can facilitate mutual understanding and alignment of expectations.
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Compliance with Ethical Standards

The study followed the ethical guidelines for conducting research with the student respondents. Before commencing the data collection process, the researcher made certain that informed consent was acquired from the parents and the student participants. The participants were provided with information regarding the study's objective, the utilization of the data, and the voluntary aspect of their involvement. In addition, the

participants' information was ensured to be confidential, and any identifiable data was eliminated during the data processing phase to safeguard their privacy.

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